

FEATURES OF THE CONTENT AND CONDUCT OF MUSIC CLASSES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: This article discusses the features of the organization of the process of musical education in different age groups of kindergarten, emphasizes the specifics of music classes, their types, as well as methods of conducting in preschool institutions.

Key words: preschool education, musical education, the specifics of planning music lessons.

A musical lesson is a form of educational work with children, during which a systematic, purposeful and comprehensive education of preschoolers is carried out, the musical abilities of each child are formed.

Music classes are the main form of educational work with children, during which pupils receive basic knowledge, skills and abilities, where children are taught various types of musical activities: listening, singing, musical and rhythmic movements and playing children's musical instruments. The musical lesson is the most difficult in its construction in kindergarten, since the alternation of various types of musical activity requires children's attention, concentration, and strong-willed efforts. The difficulty of building a lesson lies in the fact that the teacher needs to skillfully switch the attention of children from one type of activity to another, without reducing the emotional upsurge when works that are different in theme and mood are heard.

In music classes, positive personality traits are brought up:

- classes bring children together through joint actions, joyful, aesthetic experiences;
- teach a culture of behavior, require a certain concentration;
- contribute to the manifestation of mental effort, initiative, creativity. The musical activity influences other forms of children's organization;
- independent musical activity manifests itself more actively on the basis of acquired knowledge and skills;
- holidays and entertainment are more successful, because. Preliminary preparation is carried out in advance at the music lesson.

A great contribution to the development of the theory and practice of teaching preschoolers in the process of music lessons was made by well-known Russian scientists and teachers: N.A.Vetlugina, I.L.Dzerzhinskaya, N.A.Metlov and their students, who continued to actively search for new forms and methods teaching children - A.N.Zimina, O.P.Radynova and others.

The content of music lessons

The content of the lesson depends on the goals, objectives, learning tasks and age of the children. The content of a music lesson includes various types of musical activities: listening

to music, singing, rhythm (musical games and dances), teaching musical literacy, playing children's instruments.

In music classes, general educational work is carried out, special musical abilities are developed, a creative, proactive attitude to educational material is formed. The requirements for the quality of acquired skills become more complex and increase from group to group.

It is distinctive that children are taught several types of musical activities at once (listening, singing, movement, playing children's musical instruments, etc.), which is not the case in drawing, modeling, mathematics, etc.

This causes certain difficulties in conducting the lesson, since the teacher needs to skillfully switch the attention of children from one type of activity to another, without reducing their emotional upsurge. Another difficulty is the sequence of learning the educational material:

- initial acquaintance;
- mastering skills in the learning process;
- repetition, consolidation, execution of the learned material.

For example, of the three songs that are being worked on, one is well learned and expressively performed, the other is being listened to for the first time, the third is just being learned. The process of learning rhythm is similar - in a new dance, children gradually learn its individual elements, and repeat the familiar musical game.

When compiling a musical lesson, the following requirements must be considered:

1. Tasks that require sufficient mental activity, great attention, should be given to children at the beginning of the lesson.
2. Before singing, it is not recommended to perform complex physical exercises, as they disrupt the rhythm of breathing and interfere with high-quality singing.

By the end of the lesson, it is necessary to reduce the intensity of movements and the overall load. The nature of the activity evokes different emotions in the children. A fun, interesting game increases activity, so it is better to play it not at the beginning of the lesson, but after completing more complex tasks.

In the practice of teaching, it is considered appropriate to distribute various types of activities in the following sequence:

- a) in the introductory part of the lesson, small musical and rhythmic exercises are given, more often of a training nature (separate elements of dance, constructions necessary for a new dance, round dance, festive procession). These movements organize the attention of children and prepare them for more complex tasks;
- b) after the exercises, the guys sit down, listen to music and sing. Singing includes a variety of vocal exercises, performing creative tasks, exercises for the development of musical ear, learning 2-3 songs;
- c) the next stage of learning is musical and rhythmic activity in the form of a game, a cheerful dance, a round dance. Quiet tasks, alternating with dynamic ones, allow you to distribute the physical load evenly.

The structure of the lesson should be flexible and vary depending on the age of preschoolers, content, and features of the material. The teacher should be active and creative, thinking through the construction of music lessons.

Music lessons are divided into kinds and types. Types of music classes depend on the number of children participating in them:

- frontal - one age group;
- individual - held after a music lesson with lagging behind and talented children for 2-3 minutes;

- in small groups - 4-6 children, in order to prepare children for the holiday, learning to play children's musical instruments, etc. no more than 10-15 minutes;

- combined classes - before the holiday, 2, 3 age groups are combined in order to solve organizational problems.

Depending on the content and structure, classes are divided into:

type 1 - traditional or typical classes solve several educational tasks at once, where all or almost all types of children's musical activities are present. The use of traditional classes ensures systematic learning, gradualness, consistency in the assimilation of educational material, in the assimilation of certain knowledge, skills, and abilities by children;

type 2 - dominant occupations. In the structure of this type of occupation, any one of the types of musical activity dominates (listening, singing, rhythm, playing musical instruments). Such classes are used to overcome the backlog of children in one form or another of musical activity;

type 3 - thematic classes. A distinctive feature of the structure of thematic classes is that in them the musical material for all types of musical activity is united by a single theme, which is a cross-cutting one in all types of musical activity and is realized by means of musical art. The topics of classes can be different, for example: "Golden Autumn", "Seasons", "Favorite Toys", "Genres of Music", "Means of Musical Expression", etc. These are final classes that are held once a month;

type 4 - complex classes. These are classes based on one theme. It is realized by means of several types of artistic activity: artistic and speech, musical, visual, theatrical. Music is an important connecting part of the lesson. The most difficult part is the part of the complex lesson in which children perform tasks on visual activity, so the group educators conduct preliminary work with the children related to the preparation of the necessary materials. The topics of complex classes can be varied: images of nature ("Winter-Winter", "Meet the Birds"), holidays ("Spring Festival", "New Year"), life, life of people ("Merry Fair", "Skillful Hands",) and others. Comprehensive classes are not simple in their organization, so they are held once a quarter. The musical director and educators of the group take part in the preparation and conduct of the lesson. It lasts about 5-7 minutes longer than a regular session.

Organization and construction of music lessons

For music lessons in kindergarten, a certain environment should be created. Usually they are held in a hall where extraneous noises do not penetrate, interfering with the process of concentration, perception of musical works and performance of tasks. Children should come to classes in clothes that are comfortable for movement or special suits, soft shoes - czechs. Before the start of each lesson, the room is ventilated, the floor is wiped with a wet method. During the summer, classes are held outdoors whenever possible.

For music lessons in the daily routine, a constant time is allotted, a certain duration is set: 2 times a week, mainly in the morning hours in each age group, 15-18 minutes in the younger ones, 18-25 in the middle, 25-30 in the older, 35- 45 - preparatory to school groups.

While singing and listening to music, children should sit on chairs arranged in rows as close as possible to the instrument on the right hand of the music director. Chairs should be appropriate for the age and height of the children.

The class aids are prepared in advance and lie in such a way that it is convenient to take them and put them down during the lesson without wasting time. Children should not wait long for the start of the lesson, as this disorganizes and tires them.

In typical classes, when singing and listening to music, you can fix the landing sites. For example, in the younger groups, the smallest in stature, and also characterized by unstable attention, restless children sit in the front row in order to better see and hear the tasks and the performance of music by the teacher. In the middle and senior groups in the first row sit children with unformed hearing, a small range of voice, insufficiently disciplined and newly enrolled. This placement allows them to better hear the correct singing of the teacher and the children sitting in the back. They are constantly under the control of the music director and educator. Children change places as needed. In other classes, the seating of children is determined by the types of activities, the methodology of the teacher's work.

The role of the educator in the organization of music classes

The educator participates actively in the process of teaching children in music classes: in the younger groups, the educator sings with the children (without drowning out the children's singing). In the middle and senior groups, he helps to learn songs and, together with the music director, evaluates the performance of an already learned piece.

When teaching younger preschoolers musical and rhythmic movements, the teacher participates in all types of movements (exercises, dances, games), thereby activating the kids.

In the middle, senior, and especially preparatory groups, the teacher acts as necessary: shows some movement, resembles this or that construction, gives the children separate instructions in dancing, musical playing, etc.

The teacher stimulates the creativity of children: suggests a topic, distributes roles, outlines the development of the plot. The teacher should know well the musical repertoire of his age group in different types of musical activity. Joint work and mutual assistance of the musical director and educator leads to the desired results in solving the problems of the general musical education of preschoolers.

The kindergarten team should treat music lessons with due attention. During their conduct, shouts, loud conversations, the arrivals and departures of adults are unacceptable. It is also unacceptable to approach some children as future musicians and dancers. Such an attitude instills vanity and arrogance in some children, while in others it causes a feeling of envy and resentment. In the classroom, all children should behave directly, sincerely experience the successes and failures of each other, experience feelings of trust and sympathy for teachers and self-confidence.

One of the main conditions for the education of a cultural listener is a deep emotional experience of the content of musical works. It comes from interest. Given the amazing feature of children's imagination - its activity in the perception of music - one should rely on the children's musical experience, not impose ready-made movements, formulations on them in the learning process, but evoke the feeling that music is an important part of life: not entertainment, not a discipline that study, but something created by the person himself. The process of musical education should always be understandable to the child, emotionally exciting, so that he not only perceives, but also reflects on what he perceives, knows how to listen and hear.

Therefore, in the younger groups, for the most part, thematic musical lessons of the game plan are held, causing only positive emotions in relation to the environment. One of the

main tasks of such classes is to foster interest in music, the desire to listen to it, sing, dance, play accompanied by it. In the middle group, classes acquire a clearer structure. In the process of conducting them, children are required to correctly and expressively perform educational tasks. Using all types of classes, in the senior group, the teacher achieves the development of program requirements for each child

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